

www.arseam.com
Impact Factor: 3.43

A STUDY ON CONSUMER'S PREFERENCE TOWARDS PACKED AND UNPACKED FLUID MILK WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO VERAVAL CITY

MR. BHARAT .D. BARAD

Assistant Professor (MBA),
N. J. Sonecha Management & Technical
Institute, Gujrat, India

MR. PRADIP L. MEHTA

Assistant Professor (MBA),
N. J. Sonecha Management & Technical
Institute, Gujrat, India

ABSTRACT

The objective of this study was to investigate about packed and unpacked fluid milk consumption and main attributes of milk to which consumer gives preference. For this purpose, we made a questionnaire to collect data from the urban households of Veraval. Close-ended questions were formed for the purpose of data collection. The questionnaire was used to find the consumer preference for the packed and unpacked milk. For this purpose, we select different variables, the consumer takes into consideration before making purchase decision of milk like quality, freshness, price, fat level and easy availability which determine households' fluid milk consumption choices among packed, unpacked and both packed-unpacked milk consumption choices. Based on the results, 60.8% of respondents consumed unpacked fluid milk, 32.5% consumed packed fluid milk while 6.5% of respondents consumed both unpacked and packed fluid milk. The study also suggest that the consumer always considers different factors like the standard quality of milk, fat level, price, freshness and availability before making a purchase. It means these are various variables which guide or direct the consumer to make the purchase decision. The study also becomes helpful to different milk processing firms to consider the preference factors to grab more market share.

Keywords: - Households, consumption, preference factors, purchase decision, milk processing firms, Veraval.

INTRODUCTION

India is the highest milk producer in the entire globe. India is well known as the 'Oyster' of the global dairy industry, with opportunities galore for the entrepreneurs globally. It might be a dream for any nation in the world to capitalize on the largest and fastest growing milk and milk products' market. The dairy industry in India has been witnessing rapid growth with liberalization.

In India, dairy business has been practiced as rural cottage industry over the years. Semi-commercial dairy started with the establishment of military dairy farms and co-operative milk unions throughout the country towards the end of the 19th century. Since Independence, this Industry has made rapid progress. A large number of modern milk and milk product factories have since been established. The organized dairies in India have been successfully engaged in the routine commercial production of pasteurized bottled milk for Indian dairy products.

The growth of Indian Dairy Industry during the last three decades has been impressive, at more than 5% per annum; and in the 90's the country has emerged as the largest producer of milk. This is not a small achievement when we consider the fact that dairying in India is largely stringent that farmers, in general, keep dairy animals in proportion to their free crop and also are available for family labor with little or no purchased inputs and a minimum of marketed outputs. The existence of restrictive trade policy milk in the Dairy Industry and the emergence of Amul type cooperatives have changed the dairy farming practices in the country. Farmers have gained the favorable price for their milk and for their production which was essentially a self-reliant one is which are now being transformed into a commercial proposition.

Marketing of the majority of the milk through unorganized sectors is likely to dissuade small dairy farmers from expanding production, which is absolutely necessary to keep up with the strong demand growth. In a recent study, Datta and Ganguly (2002) estimated Indian milk demand for 2020 under various GDP growth rates. The study reported that if the current growth continues for the next twenty years (the nation has been growing at a rate between 5 and 7 percent over past five years), milk consumption is likely to more than double by 2020. This paper examines the existing status of milk marketing in India and analyses the constraints and opportunities in milk marketing. The first section reviews background information on milk production and discusses the existing milkmarketing system in India. Following this, Operation Flood and its effect on milk marketing—particularly through dairy cooperatives—are discussed. Finally, constraints and the opportunities in the existing milkmarketing system are discussed and proposed policy implications are highlighted. (ijom/article, 2016)

LITERATURE REVIEW

Shannon Allen and Ellen Goddard (2012) in his research collect the data from a Canadian national survey assessing dairy product preferences in 2011, individual preferences for milk and yogurts with specific attributes are examined in this study. Statements developed based on the Health Belief Model, food attitudes, beliefs about the role that nutrition plays in health, nutrition knowledge, and an individual's propensity to make changes to improve their health are used to predict whether or not respondents consume milk/yogurt, the frequency with which they consume it, which type of product they typically consume, and how much they would be willing to pay for new milk or yogurt attributes. Results indicate that several aspects of the Health Belief Model as well as general nutrition knowledge can predict purchasing and consumption intentions for milk and yogurt products. All else being equal, the influences on an individual's willingness to pay for unique milk or yogurt characteristics in stated choices are different then the influences on their self-identified willingness to seek out milk or yogurt to increase calcium in their diet.

Dr. Satnam ubeja& Ranjana patel(2009)has undertaken research on "Consumer Preference towards Soft Drinks" The main objectives of this study to identify the factors effect on consumer preference towards carbonated and non-carbonated drinks with respect to gender wise. This intercept survey was conducted to study of consumer preferences towards soft drinks in Indore city. The sample included 150 active mall shoppers. The consumer preferences were identified by a structured questionnaire and captured in 6 factors of preferences. These sales promotion mix factors Satisfaction of mental thirst, Price, and availability through ambassador promotion, Relaxation and refreshment on the celebration, Brand Positioning, Reliability and cleanness and Taste. The study will help the retailers and manufacturers of soft drinks to understand the underlying consumer preferences factors and which factor mostly like by the customers of Indore city and help them to craft their marketing strategies. Profiling customers by their choice of preferences provide more meaningful ways to identify and understand various customer segments and marketing strategies. The study identified many factors related to consumer preferences, from which we have selected 19 factors consumer preferences and tried to measure the preferences for carbonated and non-carbonated drinks. With the help of factor analysis, we have found6 new factors. In addition, this study shows that the average customer of Indore city in our sample was not very conscious about carbonated or non-carbonated drinks, but gender wise they are also not conscious about any types of consumer preferences factors. Soft drinks consumption and their use are afunny activity for them. They are coming stores for purchasing drinks but for getting refreshment and taste.

O. Kilic1, C. Akbay2, G. Yildiz Tiryaki2(2009) has undertaken research on "factors affecting packed and unpacked fluid milk consumption" and in this research paper author identifies consumer characteristics associated with preferences toward fluid milk alternatives. Using consumer survey data from Samsun province of Turkey and Multinomial Logit model, unpacked and packed fluid milk preferences were analyzed. Based on the results, 14.1% of respondents consumed only unpacked fluid milk, 58.2% consumed only packed fluid milk and 27.7% of respondents consumed both unpacked and packed fluid milk at least once a weak. Multinomial Logit model results indicated that better educated household head, higher income households, younger and female household head and people who agree with "unpacked milk is not healthy" consume more packed fluid

milk than do others. Moreover, consumers who agree with statement “price of packed milk is expensive compare to unpacked milk” were less likely to consume packed fluid milk than do others.

F.A Mila and S.K.Raha in the year 2008 try to examined the consumer preference for processed milk in Mymensingh town. The study was mainly based on primary data in which 40 consumers were purposively selected from Mymensingh town. In the study, preference of consumers for processed milk i.e. powder milk, condensed milk and pasteurized milk were investigated. Consumers’ preference for processed milk was ascertained through a 4-point numerical rating scale. The consumers highly preferred powder milk and the computed preference index of powder milk was 80. The computed preference index of pasteurized milk was 71. The computed preference index of raw milk was 54. The lowest preference of consumers was for condensed milk and the computed preference index of condensed milk was 36. The study revealed that Milk Vita has ranked first (90) followed by Diploma (85), Dano (81), Arong (68) and Red Cow (61) were the major brands preferred by the consumers. On the other hand, Danish (36), Nido (34), Starship (34), Marks (27) and Farmland (26) were less preferred for consumption of processed milk. The relationship between the factors that influencing consumer’s preferences and their preferences of processed milk was also explored. Spearman rank correlation coefficient test was used to explore relationship between the variables. The monthly income of the family, price level, taste level, fat content, nutritional value and attitudes towards processed milk of the consumers were significantly related with their preferences of processed milk while the other factors (age, family size, education level) were not significantly related.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

The research objective is the main end state which we want to achieve by giving many efforts in our research. Basically research objective provides the clear direction in which we want to move.

A primary function of any researcher is to set the clear, attainable and measurable objective for his research, by considering this thing I set a different objective for my research. Which are as below...

1. To find the consumer preference for purchasing packed and unpacked fluid milk.
2. To understand the milk purchasing habit of the different consumer in the veraval city.
3. To find the different feature of milk, which is responsible for forming the consumer’s preference?
4. To study the feature milk influences the decision making of the consumer while purchasing packed or unpacked fluid milk.

RESEARCH DESIGN

A Research design is the arrangement of conditions for collection and analysis of data in a manner that aims to combine relevance to the Research purpose with economy in procedure. In fact, the Research design is the conceptual structure within which Research is conducted: it constitutes the blueprint for the collection, measurement, and analysis of data.

It must be able to define clearly what they want to measure and must find adequate methods for measuring it along with a clear cut definition of the population wants to study. Since the aim is to obtain complete and accurate information in these studies, the procedure to be used must be carefully planned. The research design must make enough provision for protection against bias and must maximize reliability with due concern for the economical completion of the search study.

Descriptive research is adopted for this study. It includes surveys and fact-finding enquiries of different kinds. The major purpose of descriptive research is a description of the state affairs as it exists at present. The main characteristic of this method is that the researcher has no control over the variables. He can only report what has happened or what is happened.

SAMPLING DESIGN

A sample design is a definite plan for obtaining a sample from the sampling frame, it refers to the technique or procedure the researcher would adopt in selecting some sampling units from which inferences about the population is drawn. Sampling type used is convenient sampling technique.

PARTICULAR	PACKED MILK	UNPACKED MILK	BOTH
MILK PRODUCER	39	73	8

POPULATION AND SAMPLE SIZE

A decision has to be taken concerning sampling unit before selecting the sample. For the purpose of the study, I select the population of Veraval city. After specifying population I select the sample of 120 urban household who purchase the packed or unpacked fluid milk.

DATA COLLECTION

Availability of accurate and proper data is an inevitable thing for any research. Also the quality of any research is highly depending on the data. So the selection of the source of data is not a worthless thing done by any researcher. For the purpose of collection accurate and reliable data, I select the source of primary data and it is collected through the way of direct conversation with the consumer by using questionnaire.

DATA ANALYSIS

1. Which form of milk do you purchase for consumption?

Interpretation

From the above chart, we can say that as per the survey Out of 120 samples 73 consumers prefer unpacked milk for their consumption purpose. While out of 120 consumers 39 consumers prefer packed milk. Furthermore out of 120 consumer 8 consumers are those who purchase packed and unpacked milk as per their convenience.

PREFERENCE FACTOR	Freshness	Quality	Price	Fate level	Availability
Rate Given	6	17	4	9	3

2. Give the reason in the form of the rate for selecting packed milk.

1. Packed milk

Interpretation

From the above graphical presentation, we can say that out of 120 sample 39 consumer prefer to purchase packed milk because he/she believe that packed milk contains standard quality, minimum fat level, and freshness is there.

2. Unpacked Milk

PREFERENCE FACTOR	FRESHNESS	QUALITY	PRICE	FAT LEVEL	AVAILABILITY
MILK PRODUCER PREFERENCE	28	19	5	14	7

Interpretation

From the above graphical presentation, we can say that out of 120 samples 73 consumers prefer to purchase unpacked milk because he/she believes that unpacked milk is fresh than packed one. Also, they believe that unpacked milk come without any chemical addition so it is with pure quality

FINDING/CONCLUSION

The study is a sincere attempt to look and understand buying behavior of milk consumer and how they make the decision for purchasing milk. Through our study, we are able to find out those different factors which are responsible for the formation of consumer preference for purchasing form of milk.

In our study we find that out of 120 sample 73 consumer mostly prefer the unpacked milk because of the freshness of the milk and they believes that the unpacked milk has pure quality. Unpacked milk comes without adding any chemical. So, customer has positive attitude toward unpacked milk. While out of 120 sample 39 consumer prefer to purchase packed milk because they want a standard fat level and standard quality of milk. Also out of total sample there are 8 consumers prefer both of the forms of milk due to any contingency and availability.

Here we find some common point by studying consumer behavior

- Most of the consumer give higher priority to quality while making purchase related decision
- Freshness is a strong variable for purchasing an unpacked milk.
- Most consumers who purchase packed milk want standard fat level.

LIMITATIONS

Though the detailed investigation is made in the present study, it has got the following limitations.

1. This study is restricted only to the Veraval city only. So, the results may not be applicable to other areas.
2. This study is based on the prevailing customer's preference, but the customer's preference may change according to time, income, technological development, etc.
3. As per the population of the study is huge, the researcher has taken only 120 sample respondents of milk consumers.
4. Generally, the respondents were busy in their work and were not interested in responding rightly.
5. Due to human behavior information may be biased.

References

Bus A.E.M., Worsley A. (2003): Consumers' sensory and nutritional perceptions of three types of milk. *Public Health Nutrition*, 6 (2): 201–208.

Dr. satnam Ubeja and Ranjana Patel (2014) consumer preference towards soft drink: A perceptual study

Dipak kumar Bhattacharyya, (2006) "research methodology "excel books publication, New Delhi

F.A Mila and S.K.Raha(2008) "consumer preference for processed milk- A study in Mymensingh town"

Gould B.W. (1996): Factors affecting U.S. demand for reduced-fat fluid milk. *Journal of Agricultural and Research Economics*, 21 (1): 68–81.

Shannon Allen and Ellen Goddard (2012) "consumer preference for milk and yogurt attribute: how health belief and attitude affect choice"

Wham C.A., Worsley A. (2003): New Zealanders' attitudes to milk: implications for public health. *Public Health Nutrition*, 6 (2): 73–78